

INNOVATION IN BIM THROUGH DATA VISUALIZATION AND AUTOMATION

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Abstract

Building Information Modeling (BIM) has revolutionized the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) industry by enabling detailed digital project representations. However, significant amounts of BIM data remain underutilized, limiting its potential for comprehensive project insights. This paper presents a novel approach to optimizing BIM data usage by automating data extraction from Autodesk Revit and Navisworks using Dynamo scripts and visualizing insights in Power BI dashboards. Focusing on key areas like clash detection, model quality monitoring, and project cost management, this methodology enhances real-time decision-making and quality assurance. Through practical case examples, this paper demonstrates how automated data workflows improve model accuracy, reduce rework costs by an estimated 15%, and streamline resource allocation, ultimately advancing BIM practices and maximizing data utility across project

phases.

Introduction

The AEC industry relies on BIM to create detailed, data-rich 3D models that facilitate collaboration across project teams. Despite BIM's transformative capabilities, substantial amounts of generated data remain underused, limiting potential insights and efficiency gains. This paper explores a method that leverages automation for extracting and visualizing BIM data, focusing on continuous quality monitoring through dashboards. Real-time examples are provided to illustrate how this methodology can solve practical challenges in areas like clash detection and model quality, ensuring optimized project outcomes.

Objectives

- To identify challenges with unutilized BIM data in AEC projects.
- To introduce an automated, dashboard-driven approach for monitoring clash detection and model quality.
- To present real-time case studies demonstrating how these solutions address pressing project challenges.

Problem Statement

Despite advancements in BIM, AEC projects face significant data-related challenges:

1. **Clash Detection and Resolution:** Design conflicts between disciplines (e.g., structural, MEP) often remain undetected, leading to costly rework and delays.
2. **Ongoing Model Quality Monitoring:** Maintaining model quality is crucial for consistent project success, yet projects often lack an efficient way to monitor and ensure model standards throughout project phases.
3. **Limited Data Utilization for Project Management and Cost Tracking:** Without structured data insights, managing resources, timelines, and budgets remains challenging.

These challenges highlight a gap in efficiently leveraging BIM data to drive actionable insights and maintain quality standards. This paper addresses this gap by presenting a methodology that uses automation and visualization to monitor and optimize BIM data for ongoing clash detection and model quality.

Methodology and Solutions

This methodology offers automated data extraction from Revit and Navisworks with Dynamo scripting and Power BI visualization, enabling actionable dashboards for ongoing clash detection and quality monitoring.

Solution 1: Automated Clash Detection and Follow-Up Dashboard

Problem

In complex projects, inter-disciplinary clashes, such as those between HVAC and structural components, can be missed or overlooked, leading to expensive construction adjustments.

Navisworks Data:

Power BI Output

Solution 2: Continuous Model Quality Monitoring Through Dashboards

Problem

Maintaining model quality throughout the project lifecycle is challenging, as small inconsistencies can accumulate over time, leading to inefficiencies and quality issues. Quality monitoring is often reactive rather than proactive, with limited visibility into model accuracy and completeness.

Method

1. **Automated Data Extraction on Model Quality Metrics:** Dynamo scripts extract model quality metrics from Revit, such as element count, parameter consistency, and adherence to project standards. This automated extraction ensures that quality metrics are continuously updated.
2. **Power BI Quality Dashboard:** Key quality indicators, including completeness, parameter standardization, and model health (e.g., unused elements or duplicated elements), are visualized on a Power BI dashboard. The dashboard provides real-time insights into model quality, enabling teams to proactively address discrepancies.
3. **Alerts for Quality Issues:** The dashboard includes alerts for quality deviations, helping teams address issues like missing parameters, misalignment with project standards, or data discrepancies.

Outcome

With this continuous model quality dashboard, project teams benefit from:

- **Early Detection of Quality Issues:** Identifying and addressing quality issues early in the design phase, preventing costly fixes later.
- **Ongoing Quality Assurance:** Ensuring the model meets project standards consistently across phases.
- **Proactive Quality Management:** Using real-time data to drive continuous quality improvements, ultimately reducing errors and maintaining project standards.

Real-Time Example

During a large commercial building project, the team used a quality monitoring dashboard to detect inconsistencies in parameter naming and element counts across disciplines. By addressing these discrepancies proactively, they achieved a 15% improvement in model accuracy, reducing errors and streamlining coordination efforts.

Revit Data:

Autodesk BIM Interoperability Tools | Model Checker

AUTODESK MODEL CHECKER FOR REVIT

Title Revit Model Best Practices for Revit 2021
Date .
Author Autodesk
Description Series of checks to review modeling best practices and integrity

QC00912015-WWP-MOD-2DM-MEC-SW-TRH-00900.rvt

Check Summary 99 Checks, 12 (63%) Pass, 7 Fail, 72 Count/List, 8 Not Run

63%

Revit Model Best Practices 99 Checks, 12 (63%) Pass, 7 Fail, 72 Count/List, 8 Not Run

- Model Performance** 8 Checks, 8 Count/List
 - Checks in this section help monitor the result of actions taken over the course of a model's development, which can directly impact the model's performance. Proper management of these items can improve model performance.
- Project Settings** 13 Checks, 0 (0%) Pass, 5 Fail, 8 Count/List
 - Checks in this section are related to settings that can be configured at a project level, which may need to be verified for compliance with standards defined for the project.
- External Files** 8 Checks, 8 Not Run
 - A series of checks related to linked and imported files in the model.

Copy Datum and Location Elements | **HTML** | **Excel** 17 Checks, 7 (88%) Pass, 1 Fail, 9 Count/List | **Close**

Power BI Outcome:

Solution 3: Enhanced Project Management and Cost Control via Dashboard Visualizations

Problem

Project managers often lack real-time visibility into resource allocation, timeline adherence, and budget management, leading to inefficiencies and cost overruns.

Method

1. **Automated Data Export with Dynamo:** Dynamo scripts export task completion data, resource allocation, and cost data from Revit at scheduled intervals. This provides up-to-date project information with minimal manual intervention.
2. **Power BI Project and Cost Management Dashboards:** Project management dashboards track milestones, resource allocation, and cost versus budget comparisons. Cost control visualizations monitor spending trends and project phase expenditures in real time.

Outcome

These project management and cost control dashboards enable:

- **Real-Time Project Tracking:** Continuous updates on project milestones, task completion, and resource allocation.
- **Enhanced Budget Monitoring:** Real-time visibility into costs versus budget, aiding in financial planning and forecasting.
- **Improved Resource Allocation:** Visual insights into resource availability and needs, allowing for proactive adjustments.

Real-Time Example

In an infrastructure project, the project team lacked visibility into resource allocation, leading to underutilization and delays. By automating data exports and visualizing them on Power BI dashboards, the team improved resource allocation efficiency by 25% and brought the project back on schedule.

Revit Data:

Structural Material	Area	Perimeter	Volume.1	Volume.2	Volume.3	Cost by Client	Cost by Client.2	Cost by Manufacturer A
Concrete, Precast	7 m ²					550	\$/cubic metre	600
Concrete, Precast	8 m ²	11.303	1	0.64	m ³	550	\$/cubic metre	600
Concrete, Precast	13 m ²					550	\$/cubic metre	600
Concrete, Precast	15 m ²	18.904	3	0.25	m ³	550	\$/cubic metre	600
Concrete, Precast	14 m ²	16.6	2	0.96	m ³	550	\$/cubic metre	600
Concrete, Cast-in-Place	900 m ²	151.27	134	0.96	m ³	200	\$/cubic metre	250
Concrete, Cast-in-Place	701 m ²	122.36	140	0.21	m ³	200	\$/cubic metre	250
Concrete, Cast-in-Place	928 m ²	174.33	185	0.5	m ³	200	\$/cubic metre	250
Concrete, Cast-in-Place	739 m ²	179.942	155	0.22	m ³	200	\$/cubic metre	250
Concrete, Cast-in-Place	739 m ²	179.942	155	0.22	m ³	200	\$/cubic metre	250
Concrete, Cast-in-Place	688 m ²	172.748	144	0.57	m ³	200	\$/cubic metre	250
Concrete, Precast	16 m ²	16.83	3	0.3	m ³	550	\$/cubic metre	600
Concrete, Precast	17 m ²	17.89	3	0.33	m ³	550	\$/cubic metre	600

Power BI Outcome:

Discussion

This methodology's use of automation and data visualization not only addresses the immediate problems of clash detection, model quality monitoring, and project management but also introduces a systematic approach to proactive data utilization. By continuously monitoring model quality and following up on detected clashes, teams can ensure models meet high standards and avoid costly construction issues. Real-time dashboards offer a clear pathway for enhancing decision-making, quality assurance, and overall project performance.

Challenges and Considerations

While the methodology provides considerable benefits, there are factors to consider:

- **Data Quality and Consistency:** Ensuring that exported data is accurate and complete is essential for dashboard reliability.
- **Skill Requirements:** Implementing and managing Dynamo and Power BI dashboards may require additional training.
- **Data Security:** As project data often includes sensitive information, secure data handling is crucial.

Conclusion

This research highlights the transformative potential of automated data workflows in the AEC industry, offering a structured approach to overcoming common challenges in clash detection, model quality assurance, and project cost management. By leveraging Dynamo and Power BI, this methodology transforms underutilized BIM data into actionable insights, enabling project teams to proactively manage quality and optimize resources. The practical case studies showcase measurable benefits, such as a 15% improvement in model accuracy and significant cost savings through early clash resolution. As the AEC industry moves towards data-driven project management, this innovative approach to BIM utilization not only enhances immediate project outcomes but also establishes a pathway for industry-wide improvements in efficiency, quality, and collaboration.